

Improving Urology Referrals for Prostate Examinations

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Background

- Prostate cancer is responsible for the deaths of one in 41 men, and is the second leading cancer-related death among American men (American Cancer Association [ACS], 2018a)
- The ratio of urologists to the 100,000 population in California is 3.31 (American Urological Association [AUA], 2016a)
- Research and local data indicate a need to improve urology referrals for prostate examinations
- Identified barriers to proper urology referrals include contradictory guidelines, confusing decision-making aids, and providers' knowledge deficit

Purpose

- Modify and update PSA (Prostate-Specific Antigen) testing tool for primary care providers (PCPs) using the modified Delphi method to improve appropriate urology referrals

Methods

- Demographics:** A multidisciplinary Delphi panel consisting of four physicians from internal medicine, radiation oncology, surgical pathology, and urology in the Los Angeles area
- Measures of Outcomes:** Two rounds of online feedback on PSA testing guidelines to establish consensus definitions for the purpose of modifying and updating PSA testing tool
- Data Collection:** The Delphi panel convened in October 2018 for two rounds of online feedback on PSA guidelines
- Evaluation:** Consensus was reached by agreement of responses

Logic Model

Logic Model for Improving Urology Referrals for Prostate Examinations

Results

Prostate-Specific Antigen (PSA) Testing Tool

Disclaimer: This algorithm is not intended to replace the independent medical or professional judgment of health care providers

Findings

- Continued relevance of risk factors for prostate cancer
- PSA screening guidelines to follow:
 - American Urological Association (AUA)
 - American Cancer Society (ACS)
 - American Society of Clinical Oncology (ASCO)
- Emphasis on PSA value interpretation staying consistent with current urological practices
- 25% of the Delphi panel used a tool to calculate life expectancy
- 100% of the Delphi panel agreed on 50-59 age group for PSA screening, with 50% also including age groups 40-49, 60-69, and 70-79 (zero selection for 80-89 age group)

Conclusion

- The modified and updated PSA testing tool using the modified Delphi method demonstrates:
 - Appropriate application of evidence-based knowledge to clinical practice
 - Leadership through integration and utilization of multidisciplinary team
 - Incorporation of user-centered design methods to address identified clinical needs of the global health care system

Practice Application

- The modified and updated PSA testing tool will proceed to the pilot study with a group of PCPs for further evaluations before disseminating to the local PCP population to evaluate changes in referral patterns